

Third-Party Funding under the EU’s New Representative Actions Directive¹

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the role of third-party funding under the European Union’s newly enacted Representative Actions Directive. The first part gives a brief overview of the collective redress developments in the European Union and the new representative action regime. The second part focuses on third-party funding in collective redress generally and discusses the provisions in the Directive specifically relevant for third-party funding.*

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A. Introduction

After almost two decades of policy debates on collective redress, on December 24, 2020, the European Union’s (“EU”) Representative Actions Directive (“Directive”) entered into force.² The Directive requires all Member States to provide in their national laws for a collective redress mechanism in the form of a *representative action*.³ This representative action allows so-called qualified entities, such as designated consumer associations, to sue traders on behalf of consumers for violation of certain rights under EU law.⁴ Member States have to transpose the Directive by December 25, 2022, and put the new rules into force as of June 25, 2023.⁵

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² Directive (EU) 2020/1828 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2020 on representative actions for the protection of the collective interests of consumers and repealing Directive 2009/22/EC, O.J. L 409, pp. 1-27 (“Directive” or “Representative Actions Directive” or “RAD”).

³ Recital 7 RAD.

⁴ Recital 8 RAD.

⁵ Art. 24(1) RAD.

The Directive promises to be a significant step in the EU’s long-lasting struggle to increase and harmonize access to justice for consumers across Europe.⁶ To date, EU law has guaranteed consumers access to collective redress instruments only for *injunctive relief*.⁷ Under the new Directive, consumers may also seek further remedies, referred to by the Directive as *redress measures*, which include “compensation, repair, replacement, price reduction, contract termination or reimbursement of the price paid, as appropriate and as available under Union or national law.”⁸ While some Member States already do offer mechanisms to collectively seek redress measures, this is still not the case in many others; where such mechanisms do exist, their effectiveness varies greatly.⁹ Many Member States will have to significantly revise and expand their collective redress regimes to meet the requirements of the Directive.¹⁰

Whether the Directive will be a success for consumers depends, among other things, on whether Member States ensure the availability of financing for representative actions.¹¹ Litigation is expensive, and collective redress cases tend to come with a particularly significant price tag.¹² Costs include not just fees for lawyers, courts, and expert witnesses, but also significant case management expenses. Without sufficient funding, representative actions are unlikely to be initiated.¹³

⁶ A. Biard and X. Kramer, “The EU Directive on Representative Actions for Consumers: a Milestone or Another Missed Opportunity?” (2019) in *Zeitschrift für Europäisches Privatrecht ZEuP*, Vol. 27(2), pp. 249-259, at 250; B. Gsell, “Europäische Verbandsklagen zum Schutz kollektiver Verbraucherinteressen – Königs- oder Holzweg?” (2021) in *Zeitschrift für Bank- und Kapitalmarktrecht BKR*, Vol. 21(9), pp. 521-529, at 527.

⁷ See Directive 2009/22/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on injunctions for the protection of consumers’ interests, O.J. L 110, pp. 30-36 (“Injunctions Directive”).

⁸ Art. 3(10) RAD.

⁹ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council and the European Economic and Social Committee on the implementation of the Commission Recommendation of 11 June 2013 on common principles for injunctive and compensatory collective redress mechanisms in the Member States concerning violations of rights granted under Union law (2013/396/EU) of January 25, 2018, COM(2018) 40 final, at 20; Recital 6 RAD.

¹⁰ Cf. M. Hakenberg, “Die neue Verbandsklagen-Richtlinie der Europäischen Union“ (2021) in *Neue Juristische Online-Zeitschrift NJOZ*, Vol. 21(23), pp. 673-679, at 673.

¹¹ European Commission, “Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities”, Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 1; cf. also S. Voet, “Costs and funding of collective redress proceedings” in A. Stadler, E. Jeuland and V. Smith (eds.), *Collective and Mass Litigation in Europe. Model Rules for Effective Dispute Resolution* (Edward Elgar: 2020), pp. 264-295, at 264.

¹² S. Voet, “Costs and funding of collective redress proceedings” in A. Stadler, E. Jeuland and V. Smith (eds.), *Collective and Mass Litigation in Europe. Model Rules for Effective Dispute Resolution* (Edward Elgar: 2020), pp. 264-295, at 265.

¹³ Green Paper on Consumer Collective Redress, November 27, 2008, COM(2008) 794 final, at 12.

One potential source of financing for representative actions is *third-party funding* (“TPF”).¹⁴ TPF is a method of financing lawsuits in which a third party, typically a specialized litigation funder, pays the costs of the proceeding in return for a share of the recovered sums.¹⁵ While TPF has been present in some European jurisdictions on a small scale since the late 1990s, only in recent years has it become more widely adopted.¹⁶ TPF has proven to be instrumental in some of the recent mass litigation cases, such as the trucks cartel litigation, the diesel emissions litigation, or cases before the UK Competition Appeal Tribunal – and it can be expected to further grow in importance with the proliferation of representative actions under the new Directive.¹⁷ However, due to its relative novelty, many questions regarding TPF in collective redress are still open, and the legal framework under the Directive is not yet settled.

This article addresses some of these questions and discusses the role TPF can play under the Directive. The first part gives an overview of the collective redress developments on the EU level and the content of the Directive (B.). The second part focuses on TPF in collective redress generally and the provisions in the Directive relevant for TPF specifically (C.). The aim is to provide a first insight into the potentially relevant issues for the use of TPF under the representative action regime, cognizant that much will depend on the transposition of the Directive in the Member States.

B. Genesis and Content of the Representative Actions Directive

To evaluate the role of TPF under the representative action regime, it is helpful to understand the wider framework of the Directive. This section briefly recounts the developments that led to the Directive (1.) and provides an overview of the Directive’s content (2.).

¹⁴ G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019); Green Paper on Consumer Collective Redress, November 27, 2008, COM(2008) 794 final, at 13.

¹⁵ G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019), at 4-5; N. Rowles-Davies, *Third Party Litigation Funding* (Oxford University Press: 2014), at 4-5; J. Walker, S. Khouri and W. Attrill, “Funding Criteria for Class Actions” (2009) in *The University of New South Wales Law Journal*, Vol. 32(3), pp. 1036-1054, at 1036-1037.

¹⁶ B. Schumacher, *Prozessfinanzierung. Erfolgshonorierte Fremdfinanzierung von Zivilverfahren* (Schulthess: 2015), at 6-14.

¹⁷ Cf. B. Gsell, “The New European Directive on Representative Actions for the Protection of the Collective Interests of Consumers – A Huge, But Blurry Step Forward” (2021) in *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 58(5), pp. 1365-1400, at 1395.

1. Collective Redress Developments on the EU Level

The EU's initiatives towards collective redress have to be understood as a reaction to access to justice problems in situations of dispersed and mass harm. The following paragraphs explain this policy rationale behind collective redress (a) and walk through the different steps of the EU's initiatives which culminated in the Directive (b).

a) *Policy Rationale: Collective Redress for Dispersed and Mass Harm Situations*

The starting point for collective redress is a situation in which a large number of individuals are affected in similar ways by one or more wrongdoers.¹⁸ The harm per individual may be small – referred to as *dispersed harm* situations – or significant – referred to as *mass harm* situations.¹⁹ Such situations occur frequently in today's mass economy, where the acts of one or few corporations often affect thousands of consumers, investors, or business partners up and down the supply chain.

Dispersed and mass harm pose special access to justice problems. In the case of *dispersed harm*, the individual damages are often so minor that, for every individual, the prospective compensation is disproportionate to the costs of detecting the wrongdoing, instructing a lawyer, paying court fees, and going through lengthy legal proceedings.²⁰ This “rational apathy”²¹ of claimholders is problematic for two reasons. First, victims do not receive the compensation they are entitled to under the law, even where the total harm caused is significant.²² Second, wrongdoers are not held accountable, which reduces deterrence of future wrongdoing.²³

¹⁸ K. Müller, “Kollektiver Rechtsschutz in der Schweiz – Braucht es ein Gruppenvergleichsverfahren?” in W. Fellmann and S. Weber (eds.), *Haftpflichtprozess 2019* (Schulthess: 2019), pp. 13-61, at 15.

¹⁹ B. Gsell, “Europäische Verbandsklagen zum Schutz kollektiver Verbraucherinteressen – Königs- oder Holzweg?” (2021) in *Zeitschrift für Bank- und Kapitalmarktrecht BKR*, Vol. 21(9), pp. 521-529, at 522-523.

²⁰ R. van den Bergh and L. Visscher, “The Preventive Function of Collective Actions for Damages in Consumer Law” (2008) in *Erasmus Law Review*, Vol. 1(2), pp. 5-30, at 14; cf. Recital 9 RAD.

²¹ H.B. Schäfer, “The Bundling of Similar Interests in Litigation. The Incentives for Class Action and Legal Actions Taken by Associations” (2000) in *European Journal of Law and Economics*, Vol. 9(3), pp. 183-213, at 185.

²² H.B. Schäfer, “The Bundling of Similar Interests in Litigation. The Incentives for Class Action and Legal Actions Taken by Associations” (2000) in *European Journal of Law and Economics*, Vol. 9(3), pp. 183-213, at 184-185.

²³ H.B. Schäfer, “The Bundling of Similar Interests in Litigation. The Incentives for Class Action and Legal Actions Taken by Associations” (2000) in *European Journal of Law and Economics*, Vol. 9(3), pp. 183-213, at 184-185.

In cases of *mass harm*, another problem arises: if the affected parties actually do take legal action in large numbers, courts may be overburdened by thousands of duplicative claims.²⁴ This can lead to delays and contradictory judgments. For defendants, too, such a wave of litigation can mean a major organizational and financial burden. Moreover, even once claimholders make it to court, they generally face an uphill battle: they encounter a well-resourced defendant which often has strong incentives to invest heavily in the defense, lest one successful claim may trigger many others to follow.²⁵ In contrast, an individual claimholder has little incentive or possibility to invest much in a claim, for example by paying for an expensive expert opinion or specialist legal advice. This claimholder would have to bear the full cost of the investment, but the benefit would accrue also to all other claimholders in the form of a favorable precedent. This constellation creates incentives for freeriding among claimholders, with the result that claimholders refrain from investing the optimal amount and many cases are adjudicated or settled for less than they are worth.²⁶

These problems can be alleviated by *bundling claims* into one single court proceeding. For dispersed harm situations, aggregating claims and sharing costs can make collective litigation viable where individual cases would not have been so.²⁷ Thereby, collective redress opens up access to justice for claimholders, achieves compensation for victims, and increases deterrence of wrongdoing.²⁸ In mass harm situations, concentrating claims in one court proceeding preserves the resources of parties and the judiciary, ensures more consistency in adjudication, and equality of arms in terms of investment incentives.²⁹ It also makes it easier for defendants to resolve their disputes with all claimholders.

The bundling of claims into one single court proceeding can be achieved on the level of substantive law or procedural law. The *substantive law* solution involves the assignment of

²⁴ See interview with Dr. Nikolaus Stackmann, judge at the Oberlandesgericht Munich, in *beck-aktuell, Heute im Recht* (July 26, 2021) available at <https://rsw.beck.de/aktuell/daily/magazin/detail/unter-massenlast> (accessed December 15, 2021).

²⁵ T. Ulen, “An introduction to the law and economics of class action litigation” (2011) in *European Journal of Law and Economics*, Vol. 32(2), pp. 185-203, at 188-189.

²⁶ R. van den Bergh and S. Keske, “Rechtsökonomische Aspekte der Sammelklage“ in M. Casper, A. Janssen, P. Pohlmann and R. Schulze (eds.), *Auf dem Weg zu einer europäischen Sammelklage?* (Otto Schmidt: 2009), pp. 17-40, at 21; J.T. Molot, “Litigation Finance: A Market Solution to a Procedural Problem” (2010) in *Georgetown Law Journal*, Vol. 99(1), pp. 65-116, at 83.

²⁷ R. van den Bergh and L. Visscher, “The Preventive Function of Collective Actions for Damages in Consumer Law” (2008) in *Erasmus Law Review*, Vol. 1(2), pp. 5-30, at 18.

²⁸ R. van den Bergh and L. Visscher, “The Preventive Function of Collective Actions for Damages in Consumer Law” (2008) in *Erasmus Law Review*, Vol. 1(2), pp. 5-30, at 17.

²⁹ R. Dawidowicz, “Class Action Lawsuits in Europe: A Comparative and Economic Analysis” in K. Mathis (ed.), *Law and Economics in Europe. Foundations and Applications* (Springer: 2014), pp. 231-271, at 242-246.

claimholders' claims to a so-called claims entity (or claims vehicle), which then pursues the claims in its own name.³⁰ This assignment model has been used successfully in competition law damages cases and, often facilitated by information technology solutions, smaller consumer claims.³¹ The *procedural law* solutions mean that the claims of different claimholders are resolved in one single proceeding which results in a judgment binding not only parties to that dispute but also similarly situated claimholders that are not a party to that dispute. This procedural form of collective redress will be the main focus for the remainder of the article.

b) *The EU's Initiatives towards Collective Redress*

In the EU, collective redress mechanisms as a tool to enhance access to justice have long been discussed in light of Art. 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights ("ECHR"), which enshrines the right to a fair trial, and Art. 38 and 47 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union ("Charter"), which provide that EU policies are to ensure a high level of consumer protection and guarantee access to justice and due process, respectively.³²

However, the path for collective redress to become part of EU law in the form of the Directive has been rocky. Business representatives have for a long time successfully portrayed the U.S. class action as a symbol of an excessive litigation culture allegedly present in the U.S.³³ According to them, any ability of large groups of claimants to sue collectively carries the risk of abusive litigation, which may be in the interest of lawyers, but not of consumers or businesses.³⁴ On the other hand, consumer and investor protection groups respond that the problem

³⁰ T. Schreiber and M. Seegers, "Collective or Class Actions and Claims Aggregation in the EU: the Claimant's Perspective" in N. Heaton and B. Holt (eds.), *GCR Private Litigation Guide* (Law Business Research: 2021), pp. 41-54, at 44-45.

³¹ T. Makatsch and B. Kacholdt, "Kartellschadenersatz und Bündelungsmodell im Lichte von Prozessökonomie, Grundrechten und effektivem Rechtsschutz" (2021) in *Neue Zeitschrift für Kartellrecht NZKart*, Vol. 9(9), pp. 486-491.

³² C.I. Nagy, *Collective Actions in Europe. A Comparative, Economic and Transsystemic Analysis* (Springer: 2019), at 9-10; cf. Recital 4 RAD; with the Lisbon Treaty, which has marked the entry into force of the Charter, the right to access justice and due process has reached a (quasi-)constitutional level. Article 52(3) of the Charter states that the European Court of Justice, by interpreting the provisions of the Charter, shall consider them in the light of the ECHR's provisions and jurisprudence, subject to the possibility that EU law recognizes a higher level of protection, cf. M. E. Méndez Pinedo, "Access to justice as hope in the dark in search for a new concept in European law" (2011) in *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, Vol. 1(19), pp. 9-19.

³³ D.R. Hensler, "The Global Expansion of Class Actions: Power, Politics and Procedural Evolution" in B.T. Fitzpatrick and R.S. Thomas (eds.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Class Actions, An International Survey* (Cambridge University Press: 2021), pp. xvii-xxxiii, at xix.

³⁴ Cf. Green Paper on Consumer Collective Redress, November 27, 2008, COM(2008) 794 final, at 13; A. Stadler, "Kollektiver Rechtsschutz - Chancen und Risiken" (2018) in *Zeitschrift für das gesamte Handels- und Wirtschaftsrecht ZHR*, Vol. 182(6), pp. 623-655, at 635-644; M. Hakenberg, "Die neue Verbandsklagen-Richtlinie der Europäischen Union" (2021) in *Neue Juristische Online-Zeitschrift NJOZ*, Vol. 21(23), pp. 673-679, at 675.

is not with abusive litigation but with law-infringing corporations escaping liability.³⁵ Eventually, the EU legislators did become active to work on solutions.

The first legislative project on collective redress on the EU level was the directive on *injunctions* for the protection of consumers' interests, originally enacted in 1998 and revised in 2009 ("Injunctions Directive").³⁶ The Injunctions Directive grants consumer organizations the right to seek injunctions aimed at stopping certain behavior of traders that violates consumer law. However, the restriction of the remedy to injunctive relief meant that this tool was not adequate for ensuring compensation of harmed parties. For this reason, and because only consumer groups and public bodies, which have limited capital and incentives to bring a suit, were granted standing, the Injunctions Directive was not sufficiently effective in compensating consumers and deterring wrongdoing.³⁷

In the 2000s, discussions started about introducing of collective redress mechanisms also for *monetary redress*. Initially, they focused on damages for competition law violations³⁸ and later shifted to consumer law.³⁹ In 2013, the European Commission issued a recommendation in which it asked Member States to introduce collective redress mechanisms including for monetary relief ("2013 Recommendation").⁴⁰ However, the 2013 Recommendation was largely not followed.⁴¹ Many Member States did not introduce any collective redress measures, and the mechanisms that were introduced were often not effective. In 2018, the EU announced a legislative package – the New Deal for Consumers – which seeks to ensure that all European consumers will fully benefit from their rights under EU law. This New Deal comprised proposals for the amendment of several directives, including a proposal for the Representative Actions

³⁵ M. Molavi, *Collective Access to Justice. Assessing the Potential of Class Actions in England and Wales* (Bristol University Press: 2021), at 51-52.

³⁶ See B. Hess, *Europäisches Zivilprozessrecht* (De Gruyter: 2019), at 818-819 with references to earlier provisions on the protection of the collective interests of consumers.

³⁷ Recital 5 RAD.

³⁸ Green Paper Damages actions for breach of the EC antitrust rules, December 19, 2005, COM(2005) 672 final, at 9; White Paper on Damages actions for breach of the EC antitrust rules, April 2, 2008, COM(2008) 165 final, at 4.

³⁹ Green Paper on Consumer Collective Redress, November 27, 2008, COM(2008) 794 final.

⁴⁰ Commission Recommendation of 11 June 2013 on common principles for injunctive and compensatory collective redress mechanisms in the Member States concerning violations of rights granted under Union Law (2013/396/EU), O.J. L 201, pp. 60-65 ("2013 Recommendation").

⁴¹ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council and the European Economic and Social Committee on the implementation of the Commission Recommendation of 11 June 2013 on common principles for injunctive and compensatory collective redress mechanisms in the Member States concerning violations of rights granted under Union law (2013/396/EU) of January 25, 2018, COM(2018) 40 final, at 20.

Directive (“2018 Proposal”).⁴² The Directive was finally adopted in November 2020. Member States have to transpose the Directive by December 25, 2022, and apply the new rules as of June 25, 2023.⁴³

2. The Representative Actions Directive

The Directive requires all Member States to provide in their legal system for a collective redress mechanism in the form of a *representative action*.⁴⁴ Article 3(5) Directive defines a representative action as “an action for the protection of the collective interests of consumers that is brought by a qualified entity as a claimant party on behalf of consumers to seek an injunctive measure, a redress measure, or both.” The following paragraphs sketch out the representative action regime, focusing on scope (a), standing (b), consumer representation (c), and costs (d).

a) Scope – Consumer Protection Legislation as per Annex I

The scope of the Directive includes actions on behalf of consumers against traders for infringement of the provisions referred to in Annex I of the Directive.⁴⁵ These provisions cover a wide range of EU *consumer-protection subject matters*, including product liability, unfair competition, misleading advertising, consumer goods, services, travel, food, electronic commerce, telecommunication, medicinal products, energy, financial services, and data protection. Notably, competition law is not included in the scope of the Directive, an omission that is somewhat surprising, given that this was the field in which EU discussions on compensatory collective redress started.⁴⁶ In addition, the Directive only covers actions on behalf of consumers, even though small and medium-sized companies may often find themselves in a similar position as

⁴² See W. Hakenberg and E.-M. Kowollik, “New Deal for Consumers – Europäische Kollektivklage und andere Wege moderner Durchsetzung von Verbraucherrechten” (2019) in *Europäisches Wirtschafts- und Steuerrecht EWS*, pp. 61-69.

⁴³ Art. 24 RAD.

⁴⁴ Art. 1(1) RAD.

⁴⁵ Art. 2(1) RAD.

⁴⁶ Green Paper Damages actions for breach of the EC antitrust rules, December 19, 2005, COM(2005) 672 final, at 9; White Paper on Damages actions for breach of the EC antitrust rules, April 2, 2008, COM(2008) 165 final, at 4; F. Gascón Inchausti, “A new European way to collective redress? Representative actions under Directive 2020/1828 of 25 November” (2021) in *Zeitschrift für das Privatrecht der Europäischen Union*, Vol. 18(2), pp. 61-80, at 66; T. Schreiber and M. Seegers, “Collective or Class Actions and Claims Aggregation in the EU: the Claimant’s Perspective” in N. Heaton and B. Holt (eds.), *GCR Private Litigation Guide* (Law Business Research: 2021), pp. 41-54, at 47.

consumers.⁴⁷ In any event, Member States are free to include additional areas of law and beneficiaries into the scope of their transposition legislation.⁴⁸

b) Standing – Qualified Entities

A representative action cannot be brought by consumers themselves, but only by a so-called *qualified entity*.⁴⁹ A qualified entity can be either a public body or an organization – in particular consumer associations⁵⁰ – that Member States designate as entitled to bring representative actions.⁵¹ For organizations to be eligible for designation, they have to meet certain criteria. These criteria depend on whether the entity intends to bring domestic actions or cross-border actions.⁵²

Domestic actions are actions in the same Member State in which the qualified entity was designated.⁵³ For example, a consumer organization designated by Germany brings an action in German courts. For these actions, Member States are free to set their own designation criteria. The only requirement the Directive imposes is that such criteria be “consistent with the objective of [the] Directive” and ensure the representative action regime is “effective and efficient.”⁵⁴

In contrast, for *cross-border actions*⁵⁵ – actions brought in a Member State other than the one by which the qualified entity was designated – the Directive sets out binding criteria for designation: an organization which seeks this designation must (a) be a legal person and demonstrate 12 months of actual consumer protection activity, (b) have as statutory purpose the protection of consumers, (c) have a non-profit-making character, (d) not be subject of insolvency proceedings or declared insolvent, and (e) be independent and not influenced by persons other than consumers, including in the event of funding by third parties.⁵⁶

⁴⁷ S. Augenhöfer, “Die neue Verbandsklagen-Richtlinie – effektiver Verbraucherschutz durch Zivilprozessrecht?” (2021) in *Neue Juristische Wochenschrift NJW*, Vol. 74(3), pp. 113-118, at 115.

⁴⁸ Recital 18 RAD; B. Gsell, “Europäische Verbandsklagen zum Schutz kollektiver Verbraucherinteressen – Königs- oder Holzweg?” (2021) in *Zeitschrift für Bank- und Kapitalmarktrecht BKR*, Vol. 21(9), pp. 521-529, at 524; the new German coalition government has already indicated to make their collective redress mechanism available also to small enterprises, “Mehr Fortschritt Wagen – Bündnis für Freiheit, Gerechtigkeit und Nachhaltigkeit“, Koalitionsvertrag zwischen SPD, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen und FDP (2021) available at <https://www.wiwo.de/downloads/27830022/8/koalitionsvertrag-2021-2025.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 106.

⁴⁹ Art. 7(1) and (2) RAD.

⁵⁰ Recital 24 RAD; Art. 4(2) RAD.

⁵¹ Art. 3(4) RAD.

⁵² Cf. Recital 23 RAD.

⁵³ Art. 3(6) RAD.

⁵⁴ Art. 4(4) RAD.

⁵⁵ Art. 3(7) RAD.

⁵⁶ Art. 4(3)(a)-(e) RAD.

c) *Consumer Representation – Opt-in and Opt-out*

Consumers are not a claimant party to the proceedings, only the qualified entity which represents consumers is.⁵⁷ However, consumers concerned by the representative action are entitled to benefit from the outcome of the action.⁵⁸ To determine which consumers are represented by the qualified entity in an action for redress measures, Member States are free to choose either an *opt-in* model – meaning that consumers have to actively sign up – or an *opt-out* model – meaning that consumers are represented by default unless they request exclusion.⁵⁹ An opt-in regime is mandatory for consumers who are not habitually resident in the Member State in which the representative action is brought.⁶⁰ In all cases, consumers represented by the action can benefit from redress measures without the need to initiate separate proceedings.⁶¹ For injunctive relief, consumers do not have to express their wish to be included.⁶²

d) *Allocation of Costs – Loser Pays*

The Directive provides that in representative actions for redress measures, the costs of the proceedings of the successful party has to be borne by the *unsuccessful party*, subject to conditions and exceptions under national law applicable to court proceedings generally.⁶³ As the parties to the proceedings are the qualified entities and the trader, only they can, in principle, be subject to cost orders. Consumers, on the other hand, are not parties and do not have to bear costs.⁶⁴ Only in exceptional circumstances, individual consumers may be ordered to pay costs which they caused by their intentional or negligent conduct.⁶⁵ How the costs of representative actions can be funded via TPF will be discussed in the next part.

⁵⁷ Recital 36 and Art. 7(6) RAD.

⁵⁸ Art. 7(6) RAD.

⁵⁹ Art. 9(2) RAD.

⁶⁰ Art. 9(3) RAD.

⁶¹ Art. 9(6) RAD.

⁶² Art. 8(3) RAD.

⁶³ Recital 38 and Art. 12(1) RAD.

⁶⁴ Art. 12(2) RAD.

⁶⁵ Art. 12(3) RAD.

C. TPF in Collective Redress and under the Representative Actions Directive

The hurdles in terms of costs, risks, and organizational effort in collective redress are significant.⁶⁶ This part, in a first step, sketches out the lifecycle of a collective redress case and shows how TPF can help overcome these hurdles (1). In a second step, the role of TPF under the Directive will be discussed (2).

1. TPF in Collective Redress

a) *The Lifecycle of a Collective Redress Case*

A collective redress case has to be understood as a complex project which includes various steps.⁶⁷ The starting point for a collective redress case is the *identification* of a situation where mass or dispersed harm occurred. This situation will then need to be *evaluated* from factual, legal as well as financial perspectives. These evaluations may involve *experts* from various fields, such as economic experts in competition law cases, valuation experts in securities cases, and technical experts in product safety cases. In addition, *evidence* and other *data* from claimholders may need to be collected, managed, and analyzed.⁶⁸

Throughout the case, continuing *interaction with claimholders* is an important task that significantly increases the complexity and cost of collective redress cases.⁶⁹ If a case is to be dealt with through an opt-in mechanism, a so-called *book building* is necessary, i.e., the process of putting together a group of claimholders for the action.⁷⁰ Book building can entail significant efforts and expenses. In the typical mass or dispersed harm scenario, by definition, a large

⁶⁶ S. Voet, “Costs and funding of collective redress proceedings” in A. Stadler, E. Jeuland and V. Smith (eds.), *Collective and Mass Litigation in Europe. Model Rules for Effective Dispute Resolution* (Edward Elgar: 2020), pp. 264-295, at 265.

⁶⁷ S. Voet, “Costs and funding of collective redress proceedings” in A. Stadler, E. Jeuland and V. Smith (eds.), *Collective and Mass Litigation in Europe. Model Rules for Effective Dispute Resolution* (Edward Elgar: 2020), pp. 264-295, at 265; see for an overview of the different stages of a class action: V. Waye and V. Morabito, “Financial arrangements with litigation funders and law firms in Australian class actions” in W.H. van Boom (ed.), *Litigation, Costs, Funding and Behaviour* (Routledge: 2017), pp. 155-200, at 173.

⁶⁸ F. Gascón Inchausti, “A new European way to collective redress? Representative actions under Directive 2020/1828 of 25 November” (2021) in *Zeitschrift für das Privatrecht der Europäischen Union*, Vol. 18(2), pp. 61-80, at 78.

⁶⁹ F. Gascón Inchausti, “A new European way to collective redress? Representative actions under Directive 2020/1828 of 25 November” (2021) in *Zeitschrift für das Privatrecht der Europäischen Union*, Vol. 18(2), pp. 61-80, at 78.

⁷⁰ V. Waye and V. Morabito, “Financial arrangements with litigation funders and law firms in Australian class actions” in W.H. van Boom (ed.), *Litigation, Costs, Funding and Behaviour* (Routledge: 2017), pp. 155-200, at 177-178.

number of claimholders are involved. These claimholders need to be identified, provided with information about the case and the necessary documentation, and be persuaded to opt in.⁷¹ Often, this means running campaigns on both traditional media and social media, or outreach campaigns, including through consumer or trade associations. In addition, tailor-made IT platforms are frequently required to facilitate the sign-up process. If the case is to be dealt with in an opt-out mechanism, claimholders need to be *notified* about their participation in the action and informed about their right to opt out.⁷² Fulfilling these due process requirements likewise can require substantial resources and expertise.

Further, a typical case may involve various rounds of settlement negotiations, document discovery, motions, hearings, certification, trial, and appeals. Once a successful judgment is obtained, it still needs to be enforced. Enforcement may involve asset tracing and enforcement proceedings, potentially in multiple jurisdictions. The sums obtained from the defendant will eventually need to be fairly distributed to claimholders. If the case is not successful, adverse costs often need to be borne by the claimant party. Finally, as mass and dispersed harm situations often cross borders and involve regulatory and criminal proceedings, the coordination with these parallel proceedings makes collective redress cases potentially even more complex.

As becomes evident from this overview, the cost, risk, and organizational effort required to bring a collective redress case successfully to completion are significant.⁷³ The next section will discuss how these hurdles can be overcome with the help of TPF.

b) TPF as a Method for Enabling Collective Redress

As mentioned, TPF is an arrangement in which a third party, typically a specialized litigation funder, provides the capital to cover the costs of a proceeding in return for a share of the recovered sums.⁷⁴ If the case is successful, the funder receives back the provided capital plus a success fee.⁷⁵ This fee is typically calculated as a percentage of recovery or a multiple of the capital

⁷¹ Cf. F. Gascón Inchausti, “¿Hacia un modelo europeo de tutela colectiva?” (2021) in *Cuadernos de Derecho Transnacional*, Vol. 12, pp. 1290-1323, at 1320.

⁷² Cf. Art. 13(2) RAD.

⁷³ S. Voet, “Costs and funding of collective redress proceedings” in A. Stadler, E. Jeuland and V. Smith (eds.), *Collective and Mass Litigation in Europe. Model Rules for Effective Dispute Resolution* (Edward Elgar: 2020), pp. 264-295, at 265.

⁷⁴ G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019), at 4-5; N. Rowles-Davies, *Third Party Litigation Funding* (Oxford University Press: 2014), at 4-5; J. Walker, S. Khouri and W. Attrill, “Funding Criteria for Class Actions” (2009) in *The University of New South Wales Law Journal*, Vol. 32(3), pp. 1036-1054, at 1036-1037.

⁷⁵ J. Walker, S. Khouri and W. Attrill, “Funding Criteria for Class Actions” (2009) in *The University of New South Wales Law Journal*, Vol. 32(3), pp. 1036-1054, at 1036-1037.

provided, or a combination thereof.⁷⁶ If the case is lost, the funder receives nothing and bears the loss of the capital provided and, where applicable, adverse costs.⁷⁷

TPF as a financing method offers two key benefits to a funded party.⁷⁸ First, the funder provides *liquidity* to pay fees and expenses. Second, the funder takes on the *financial risk* of the lawsuit – if the case is lost, the funder bears all losses and the funded party does not lose any money. It is this second function, the risk transfer, which is the fundamental difference of TPF to a traditional loan.⁷⁹ While a loan also provides liquidity, the financial risk of the lawsuit remains with the party taking the loan, as the loan has to be repaid in any event.⁸⁰ In contrast, TPF does not have to be repaid if the case is lost – it is the funder who bears the risk of total loss.⁸¹

The risk transfer has important implications for the pricing of TPF.⁸² For TPF to make economic sense for the funder, the funder has to be compensated for the risk transfer in addition to being compensated for providing liquidity.⁸³ Therefore, one should expect the fair market price of TPF, measured as a share of recovery, to be significantly higher than interest rates for traditional loans.⁸⁴ This is why the price of TPF can be several multiples of the amount of capital provided. Ultimately, the right price has to be determined on a case-by-case basis, taking into account the capital provided, the risks involved, the likely duration until recovery, as well as interest rates and risk premiums determined by financial markets.⁸⁵

⁷⁶ N. Rowles-Davies, *Third Party Litigation Funding* (Oxford University Press: 2014), at 4.

⁷⁷ J. Walker, S. Khouri and W. Attrill, “Funding Criteria for Class Actions” (2009) in *The University of New South Wales Law Journal*, Vol. 32(3), pp. 1036-1054, at 1036-1037.

⁷⁸ L. Visscher and M. Faure, “A Law and Economics Perspective on the EU Directive on Representative Actions” (2021) in *Journal of Consumer Policy*, Vol. 44, pp. 455-482, at 463.

⁷⁹ M. Dimde, *Rechtsschutzzugang und Prozessfinanzierung im Zivilprozess. Eine ökonomische Analyse des Rechts* (Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag: 2003), at 184-185.

⁸⁰ A. Siebert-Reimer, *Der Anspruch auf Erstattung der Kosten der Prozessfinanzierung* (Duncker & Humblot: 2017), at 67.

⁸¹ M. Dimde, *Rechtsschutzzugang und Prozessfinanzierung im Zivilprozess. Eine ökonomische Analyse des Rechts* (Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag: 2003), at 184-185.

⁸² A. Hickson, “High risk, high return” in S. Friel (ed.), *The Law and Business of Litigation Finance* (Bloomsbury Professional: 2020), pp. 365-396.

⁸³ A. Hickson, “High risk, high return” in S. Friel (ed.), *The Law and Business of Litigation Finance* (Bloomsbury Professional: 2020), pp. 365-396, at 392.

⁸⁴ I.N. Tzankova and X.E. Kramer, “From Injunction and Settlement to Action: Collective Redress and Funding in the Netherlands” in A. Uzelac and S. Voet (eds.), *Class Actions in Europe. Holy Grail or Wrong Trail?* (Springer: 2021), pp. 97-130, at 112.

⁸⁵ A. Hickson, “High risk, high return” in S. Friel (ed.), *The Law and Business of Litigation Finance* (Bloomsbury Professional: 2020), pp. 365-396, at 391-392; N. Rowles-Davies, *Third Party Litigation Funding* (Oxford University Press: 2014), at 4.

Depending on the involvement of the funder in the litigation, two types of TPF can be distinguished: passive and active.⁸⁶ *Passive TPF* means that the funder pays the costs, but the control and the management of the litigation stays in the hands of the claimholders and their counsel, a consumer association, or a claims aggregation entity.⁸⁷ The funder carries out a due diligence of the merits of the claim, strategy proposed by the lawyers, track record of the lawyers, quantum, likely duration, expected costs, and the solvency of the counterparty.⁸⁸ Once the funder decides to fund the claim, they pay the costs and – while periodically receiving updates and monitoring the progress – wait until the case comes to an end, hoping to get a share of the recovery, without managing the case.⁸⁹

In contrast, in *active TPF*, the funder is actively involved in managing the case.⁹⁰ In this scenario, the funder not only provides liquidity and risk transfer, but also strategic expertise and administrative support.⁹¹ In active TPF, the funder may have significant control over the case and may contract for rights to choose and instruct the lawyer, determine litigation strategy, and decide on settlement offers.⁹² In addition, the funder may be involved in daily operations, such as collecting and managing evidence and coordinating relationships with experts and claimholders. Active TPF can be useful where a case requires special management skills or where a funder can offer special expertise in a particular type of dispute. To what extent such an active involvement of the funder is possible depends on the applicable regulatory and ethical framework. To avoid regulatory issues, the claims of the original claimholders are sometimes transferred by assignment to the funder (or a special purpose vehicle controlled by the funder).⁹³ The funder then brings the claims in its own name and according to its own strategy, subject to

⁸⁶ G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019), at 138.

⁸⁷ Passive funding has been compared to placing a bet on a horse. “After learning everything possible about the horse and its jockey, a decision is made whether to bet on the horse, and after the bet is made, the bettor sits on the sidelines and watches the race. The bettor neither coaches from the sidelines nor gets involved in decisions about how to ride the horse or manage the course or jockey. Similarly, after deciding to provide funding, a funder in this model does not get involved in choice of counsel, settlement, litigation strategy, or negotiations.” M. DeStefano, “Claim Funders and Commercial Claim Holders: A Common Interest or a Common Problem?” (2014) in *DePaul Law Review*, Vol. 63(2), pp. 305-376, at 320-323.

⁸⁸ J. Walker, S. Khouri and W. Attrill, “Funding Criteria for Class Actions” (2009) in *The University of New South Wales Law Journal*, Vol. 32(3), pp. 1036-1054, at 1040-1045.

⁸⁹ C. Veljanowski, “Third-Party Litigation Funding in Europe” (2012) in *Journal of Law, Economics & Policy*, Vol. 8(3), pp. 405-449, at 408.

⁹⁰ M. DeStefano, “Claim Funders and Commercial Claim Holders: A Common Interest or a Common Problem?” (2014) in *DePaul Law Review*, Vol. 63(2), pp. 305-376, 323-325.

⁹¹ G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019), at 146-155.

⁹² G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019), at 146-155.

⁹³ G.M. Solas, *Third Party Funding. Law, Economics and Policy* (Cambridge University Press: 2019), at 146-155.

conditions agreed in the assignment and litigation funding agreements. The original claimholders have contractual rights to monetary payouts in case of success.

The passive and active forms of TPF described are idealized types; in practice, aspects of the two may be combined. It may well be that the funder takes a generally passive approach but requires to have a voice on settlement. On the other hand, it may be that the funder is actively involved in gathering evidence and liaising with experts, while refraining from interference with litigation strategy or settlement decisions. The specific level of involvement of the funder depends on the needs of the claimholders in a given case, the funder's business model, and the regulatory framework applicable. The next section will analyze what role TPF can play under the Directive.

2. TPF under the Representative Actions Directive

TPF was a controversial topic in the discussions leading up to the Directive.⁹⁴ On the one hand, organizations representing business interests warned that TPF might “lead to opportunistic or speculative litigation and unreasonable fees at the expense of consumers.”⁹⁵ On the other hand, there has been a growing recognition that TPF can play an important role in enabling access to justice and levelling the playing field in collective redress cases.⁹⁶ This section will, first, establish that there is indeed a need for TPF for the representative action regime. Second, the rules relevant for funding will be presented, and the implications of those rules for TPF will be discussed.

a) *Need for TPF*

For the representative action regime to work properly, TPF will likely be a key enabling factor, as it seems to be the only realistically available funding method.⁹⁷ As has been seen, the costs

⁹⁴ A. Biard and X. Kramer, “The EU Directive on Representative Actions for Consumers: a Milestone or Another Missed Opportunity?” (2019) in *Zeitschrift für Europäisches Privatrecht ZEuP*, Vol. 27(2), pp. 249-259, at 257; cf. J. Peysner, “Playing the man not the ball” in W.H. van Boom (ed.), *Litigation, Costs, Funding and Behavior* (Routledge: 2017), pp. 55-79.

⁹⁵ *Joint Business Statement on the Proposal on Representative Actions (Collective Redress)* of November 30, 2018, available at https://www.buinessurope.eu/sites/buseur/files/media/position_papers/legal/2018-11-30_joint_business_statement_on_representative_actions_proposal_collective_redress.pdf (accessed December 15, 2021), at 3.

⁹⁶ M. Molavi, *Collective Access to Justice. Assessing the Potential of Class Actions in England and Wales* (Bristol University Press: 2021), at 105-113; B. Gsell, “The New European Directive on Representative Actions for the Protection of the Collective Interests of Consumers – A Huge, But Blurry Step Forward” (2021) in *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 58(5), pp. 1365-1400, at 1395.

⁹⁷ B. Gsell, “The New European Directive on Representative Actions for the Protection of the Collective Interests of Consumers – A Huge, But Blurry Step Forward” (2021) in *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 58(5), pp. 1365-1400, at 1395.

of collective redress actions can be significant and may well run into the millions.⁹⁸ Standing to bring representative actions is limited to *qualified entities* which, at least in cross-border cases, must have a not-for-profit character.⁹⁹ Consumer organizations, the Directive’s preferred candidates for qualified entities, are notoriously underfunded and do not have the staff necessary to bring representative actions without external funding.¹⁰⁰ A provision in the 2018 Proposal that would have obliged Member States to provide *public funding* to qualified entities for bringing representative actions was removed in the legislative process, indicating the Member States’ lack of inclination to fund qualified entities through public funds.¹⁰¹ Instead, the Directive now includes a statement that “[...] Member States should not be required to finance representative actions.”¹⁰² Furthermore, *contingency fees* for lawyers, through which class actions are financed in the U.S., are still largely restricted in most Member States.¹⁰³ While *individual claimholder contributions*, *legal aid*, and *legal expenses insurance* are in principle possible funding sources, these approaches come with significant administrative burden and are not feasible in most cases.¹⁰⁴ In addition, legal aid and legal expenses insurance are unlikely to apply for all claimholders concerned by a representative action, further complicating the funding process. One promising option that is often discussed is the establishment of a public fund financed by fines and contributions from successful cases.¹⁰⁵ However, even if established, such a fund would most likely not be able to fund all meritorious cases. Therefore, TPF is necessary if the Directive is to be more than a well-meaning piece of legislation with little practical benefit

⁹⁸ The Litigation Funding Agreement in *Merricks v Mastercard* provides for costs and disbursements of £45.1 million plus an adverse cost cover of £15 million, *Merricks v Mastercard* ([2021] CAT 28), available at https://www.catribunal.org.uk/sites/default/files/2021-08/2021.08.18_Merricks_Judgment_Final.pdf (accessed December 15, 2021), at 9.

⁹⁹ Art. 4(3)(c) RAD.

¹⁰⁰ European Commission, “Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities”, Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 1.

¹⁰¹ Art. 15(1) 2018 Proposal compared to Art. 20(1) and (2) RAD.

¹⁰² Recital 70 RAD.

¹⁰³ S. Voet, “Costs and funding of collective redress proceedings” in A. Stadler, E. Jeuland and V. Smith (eds.), *Collective and Mass Litigation in Europe. Model Rules for Effective Dispute Resolution* (Edward Elgar: 2020), pp. 264-295, at 274.

¹⁰⁴ Cf. I.N. Tzankova, “Funding of Mass Disputes: Lessons from the Netherlands” (2012) in *Journal of Law, Economics & Policy*, Vol. 8(3), pp. 549-591.

¹⁰⁵ A. Stadler, “Third-Party Funding of Mass Litigation in Germany: Entrepreneurial Parties – Curse of Blessing?” in L. Cadet, B. Hess and M Requejo Isidro (eds.), *Privatizing Dispute Resolution. Trends and Limits* (Nomos: 2019), pp. 209-232, at 229-232.

for consumers.¹⁰⁶ Whether and to what extent TPF is possible under the Directive will be discussed next.

b) Admissibility of TPF

According to Art. 10(1) Directive, Member States are free to decide whether they want to allow or prohibit funding by third parties for representative actions.¹⁰⁷ This means that TPF is, in principle, *admissible* under the Directive.¹⁰⁸

However, insofar as Member States do allow TPF, they have to observe a number of principles and rules.¹⁰⁹ These principles and rules are to be read in light of the aim to find a “balance between improving consumers’ access to justice and providing appropriate safeguards for traders to avoid abusive litigation that would unjustifiably hinder the ability of businesses to operate in the internal market.”¹¹⁰ Accordingly, as Art. 10(1) Directive provides, Member States have to ensure that, in cases of funding by a third party, “conflicts of interests are prevented and that funding by third parties that have an economic interest in the bringing or the outcome of the representative action for redress measures does not divert the representative action away from the protection of the collective interests of consumers.”¹¹¹ The Directive provides some guidance on how Member States should achieve these goals in that it prohibits certain funding constellations and limits the influence a funder may have on the decisions of a qualified entity.

c) Prohibited Funding Constellations

Article 10(2)(b) Directive prohibits funding where the funder is either a *competitor of the defendant* or an entity *dependent on the defendant*.¹¹² In these constellations, it is easy to see that such funding provider could have interests that diverge from those of consumers. In the case of funding by a competitor, the goal of the action may be to maximize harm to the defendant, for example by unjustifiably damaging the reputation or reducing the market share of the defendant,

¹⁰⁶ S. Augenhöfer, “Die neue Verbandsklagen-Richtlinie – effektiver Verbraucherschutz durch Zivilprozessrecht?” (2021) in *Neue Juristische Wochenschrift NJW*, Vol. 74(3), pp. 113-118, at 117.

¹⁰⁷ Art. 10(1) RAD; S. Augenhöfer, “Die neue Verbandsklagen-Richtlinie – effektiver Verbraucherschutz durch Zivilprozessrecht?” (2021) in *Neue Juristische Wochenschrift NJW*, Vol. 74(3), pp. 113-118, at 117.

¹⁰⁸ A. Biard and S. Voet, “Collective Redress in the EU: Will it Finally Come True?” in A. Uzelac and S. Voet (eds.), *Class Actions in Europe. Holy Grail or Wrong Trail?* (Springer: 2021), pp. 287-299 at 295; B. Rentsch, “Kollektiver Rechtsschutz unter der EU-Verbandsklagerichtlinie: Systemwettbewerb unter Brüssel Ia?” (2021) in *Europäische Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsrecht EuZW*, Vol. 32(12), pp. 524-533, at 529.

¹⁰⁹ F. Gascón Inchausti, “¿Hacia un modelo europeo de tutela colectiva?” (2021) in *Cuadernos de Derecho Transnacional*, Vol. 12, pp. 1290-1323, at 1304.

¹¹⁰ Recital 10 RAD.

¹¹¹ Art. 10(1) RAD (emphasis added).

¹¹² This rule was already included in Art. 16(b) 2013 Recommendation and Art. 7(2)(b) 2018 Proposal.

which may not serve the interests of consumers. Worse, in the case of funding by a dependent party, the goal might be to achieve a result most favorable for the defendant, which is likely the opposite of what would be in the consumers' interest.

A comparison of these prohibited constellations with commercial TPF shows that a ban of TPF under the Directive would not be justified.¹¹³ In TPF, a funder has in principle the same interest as the claimholders, i.e., to bring the action to a successful outcome and to maximize the value of the proceeds of a judgment or settlement.¹¹⁴ In contrast, a funder does not have an interest in harming traders per se, as may be the case for a competitor, or obtaining a judgment that would be against the interests of consumers, as may be the case for an entity which is dependent on the defendant. In line with these findings, a provision which would have provided “that third party funding is prohibited, except in the case of individual contributions,” originally proposed by the Committee on Legal Affairs of the European Parliament, was rejected in the legislative process and not included into the Directive.¹¹⁵ Accordingly, the Directive prohibits only the two funding constellations mentioned above, which are were viewed as prone to conflicts of interests. To the contrary, TPF offered by a commercial litigation funder who is neither a competitor of nor dependent on the defendant is not barred under the Directive.¹¹⁶

d) *Limitations on Funder Influence*

As discussed, TPF may take various forms in terms of the level of funder involvement. This section discusses the provisions that restrict the influence a funder may exert under the Directive. In this regard, the Directive sets out rules which apply to all actions for redress measures

¹¹³ Cf. B. Gsell, “The New European Directive on Representative Actions for the Protection of the Collective Interests of Consumers – A Huge, But Blurry Step Forward” (2021) in *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 58(5), pp. 1365-1400, at 1396-1397.

¹¹⁴ B. Rentsch, “Kollektiver Rechtsschutz unter der EU-Verbandsklagerichtlinie: Systemwettbewerb unter Brüssel Ia?” (2021) in *Europäische Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsrecht EuZW*, Vol. 32(12), pp. 524-533, at 530.

¹¹⁵ Draft Report on the proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on representative actions for the protection of the collective interests of consumers, and repealing Directive 2009/22/EC (COM(2018)0184 – C8-0149/2018 – 2018/0089(COD)), available at https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/JURI-PR-628647_EN.pdf?redirect (accessed December 15, 2021), Amendment 30, at 20; see A. Biard and X. Kramer, “The EU Directive on Representative Actions for Consumers: a Milestone or Another Missed Opportunity?” (2019) in *Zeitschrift für Europäisches Privatrecht ZEuP*, Vol. 27(2), pp. 249-259, at 256-257.

¹¹⁶ B. Gsell, “The New European Directive on Representative Actions for the Protection of the Collective Interests of Consumers – A Huge, But Blurry Step Forward” (2021) in *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 58(5), pp. 1365-1400, at 1397; this is also the position of the European Commission: “Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities”, Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 2.

– Art.10(2)(a) – and independence criteria for qualified entities that apply only to cross-border actions – Art. 4(3)(e) and (f).

i) Limitations on Funder Influence in a Specific Case

According to Art. 10(2)(a) Directive, in *all actions for redress measures*, Member States must ensure that

“the decisions of qualified entities in the context of a representative action, including decisions on settlement, are *not unduly influenced* by a third party in a manner that would be *detrimental to the collective interests of the consumers concerned* by the representative action.”¹¹⁷

While this provision limits the influence a funder may have, it does not prohibit all influence. Instead, influence is only prohibited if it is *undue* and *detrimental to the collective interest of consumers* concerned by the action. This is a notable difference to the 2013 Recommendation and the 2018 Proposal, both of which prohibited *any* influence.¹¹⁸ What exactly constitutes such an *undue* influence is difficult to tell.¹¹⁹ In any event, this provision seems to allow *some* influence of a funder on the decisions of a qualified entity, including on a decision on settlement, as long as such influence is not undue. Such a solution seems reasonable. To put it in the words of one notable commentator:

“Where a third-party funder takes the procedural risk it has a legitimate interest to have some influence on the strategy and on basic decisions of the plaintiff such as withdrawal of the action or negotiating a settlement. To ban such an influence completely seems neither adequate nor practical.”¹²⁰

In line with this view, it should not be considered an undue influence if, for example, the funder reserves the right to request a determination of the reasonableness of a settlement by a neutral third party in case the funder and the qualified entity are of different opinion.¹²¹

¹¹⁷ Emphasis added.

¹¹⁸ Art. 7(2)(a) 2018 Proposal and Art. 16(a) 2013 Recommendation.

¹¹⁹ B. Rentsch, “Kollektiver Rechtsschutz unter der EU-Verbandsklagerichtlinie: Systemwettbewerb unter Brüssel Ia?” (2021) in *Europäische Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsrecht EuZW*, Vol. 32(12), pp. 524-533, at 529.

¹²⁰ A. Stadler, “Third-Party Funding of Mass Litigation in Germany: Entrepreneurial Parties – Curse of Blessing?” in L. Cadet, B. Hess and M Requejo Isidro (eds.), *Privatizing Dispute Resolution. Trends and Limits* (Nomos: 2019), pp. 209-232, at 227.

¹²¹ See Art. 13.2 of the Code of Conduct for Litigation of the Association of Litigation Funders of England and Wales, which states that “if there is a dispute between the Funder, Funder’s Subsidiary or Associated Entity and the Funded Party about settlement or about termination of the LFA, a binding opinion shall be obtained from a Queen’s Counsel who shall be instructed jointly or nominated by the Chairman of the Bar Council.”, available

Further, according to the wording of Art. 10(2)(a) Directive, a funder may influence the decisions of a qualified entity *in favor* of consumers. Accordingly, it should not be problematic for a funder to advise a qualified entity on strategic questions, provide operational support, or help monitor class counsel’s performance.¹²² However, some of the more far-reaching forms of funder involvement that are sometimes present in active TPF, such as unilaterally choosing the lawyer, determining strategy, or unilaterally deciding on settlement, may not be available under the Directive. Ultimately, how far such funder involvement may go will be a question to be determined by national law and the courts.

In cases where justified doubts arise with respect to compliance with Art. 10(1) and (2) Directive, courts and administrative authorities are empowered to assess such compliance under Art. 10(3) Directive. “To that end, qualified entities shall disclose to the court or administrative authority a financial overview that lists sources of funds used to support the representative action.” Importantly, the disclosure happens only to the court, but no to the defendant.¹²³ Disclosure of details of the funding arrangement could reveal strategically important information, in which the defendant does not have a legitimate interest.¹²⁴ The disclosed information should enable courts and administrative authorities to assess whether Art. 10(1) and (2) Directive are complied with.¹²⁵

For cases in which these provisions are not complied with, Art. 10(4) Directive provides that courts or administrative authorities should be able to take appropriate measures to ensure compliance. For example, a court may order changes to a funding arrangement or require a qualified entity to refuse funding.¹²⁶ If necessary, standing of the qualified entity can be rejected for the action in question, in which case, however, the rights of the consumers shall not be affected.¹²⁷

at <https://associationoflitigationfunders.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Code-Of-Conduct-for-Litigation-Funders-at-Jan-2018-FINAL.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021).

¹²² Cf. B. Rentsch, “Kollektiver Rechtsschutz unter der EU-Verbandsklagerichtlinie: Systemwettbewerb unter Brüssel Ia?” (2021) in *Europäische Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsrecht EuZW*, Vol. 32(12), pp. 524-533, at 533; V. Waye and V. Morabito, “Financial arrangements with litigation funders and law firms in Australian class actions” in W.H. van Boom (ed.), *Litigation, Costs, Funding and Behaviour* (Routledge: 2017), pp. 155-200, at 184.

¹²³ European Commission, “Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities”, Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 3.

¹²⁴ I.N. Tzankova and X.E. Kramer, “From Injunction and Settlement to Action: Collective Redress and Funding in the Netherlands” in A. Uzelac and S. Voet (eds.), *Class Actions in Europe. Holy Grail or Wrong Trail?* (Springer: 2021), pp. 97-130, at 117.

¹²⁵ Recital 52 RAD.

¹²⁶ Art. 10(4) RAD.

¹²⁷ Art. 10(4) RAD.

ii) Limitations on Funder Influence on a Qualified Entity Generally

For *cross-border actions*, the Directive’s designation criteria for qualified entities apply. Article 4(3)(e) Directive requires for the designation of qualified entities that they be

“*independent and not influenced* by persons other than consumers, in particular by traders, who have an economic interest in the bringing of any representative action, *including in the event of funding by third parties*, and, to that end, has established procedures to prevent such influence as well as to prevent conflicts of interest between itself, its funding providers and the interests of consumers.”¹²⁸

At first sight, this provision seems to restrict the influence a funder may exert on qualified entities in cross-border actions more severely than in domestic actions, as such restriction is not limited to *undue* influence.¹²⁹ However, the following considerations suggest that this provision is not directed at the influence a funder may have *in a specific case*. First, Art. 4(3)(e) Directive is a *designation criterion*, and designation happens irrespective of a specific case. It is not possible or at least not practical to make designation dependent on the funding arrangements in specific cases which will occur only in the future. Second, if Art. 4(3)(e) Directive were to be understood as a limit on the funder’s influence under a specific funding arrangement, courts should be able to *review compliance* in a specific case. However, it is doubtful whether such a review by courts of compliance with Art. 4(3)(e) Directive in individual cases is possible under the Directive. Article 6(3) Directive provides that courts and administrative authorities, in principle, have to accept other Member States’ designation of qualified entities for the purpose of cross-border actions, reserving only the “right of the court or administrative authority sei[z]ed to examine whether the statutory purpose of the qualified entity justifies its taking action in a specific case.” While defendants in a representative action may raise to the court seized concerns regarding the compliance with designation criteria, it is for the designating Member State – not the court seized – to investigate the concerns and, if appropriate, revoke the designation.¹³⁰ Article 10(3) Directive gives courts and administrative authorities the power to review compliance with Art. 10(1) and (2), but not with Art. 4(3)(e) Directive. Third, according to Art. 5(4) Directive, the *consequence of non-compliance* with designation criteria is that the designating Member State may revoke designation, which is hardly an appropriate reaction to undue funder

¹²⁸ Emphasis added.

¹²⁹ B. Rentsch, “Kollektiver Rechtsschutz unter der EU-Verbandsklagerichtlinie: Systemwettbewerb unter Brüssel Ia?” (2021) in *Europäische Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsrecht EuZW*, Vol. 32(12), pp. 524-533, at 529.

¹³⁰ Recitals 29, 30 and Art. 5(4) RAD.

influence in a specific case and inconsistent with the regime set out in Art. 10 Directive, which provides that courts may order changes to or refusal of the funding or reject standing for the action in question, but not that courts may revoke designation of the qualified entity. This analysis thus suggests that the level of influence a funder may have in a given case is regulated exclusively in Art. 10 Directive, not in Art. 4(3) Directive. If indeed a different level of permissible funder involvement in cross-border cases was the aim of the legislator, Art. 10(2)(a) Directive would have been the right place to make this difference. As this provision does not distinguish between domestic and cross-border actions, the same restrictions on a funder's influence – the ones of Art. 10(2)(a) Directive – should apply in both cases.

Accordingly, Art. 4(3)(e) Directive should be interpreted so as to ensure that the qualified entity is independent from interests other than consumer interests in ways that can be assessed at the time of designation, outside of the context of a particular case. Such an interpretation would mean that a qualified entity should in particular not be controlled by a trader with an economic interest in the bringing of any representative action or a funder from which it obtains TPF – for example by way of having a majority equity stake in a qualified entity, being the exclusive funding provider, or having a majority of representatives on the supervisory or management board of the qualified entity. This view is supported by the fact that Art. 4(3)(e) Directive requires that a qualified entity have “established procedures to prevent such influence as well as to prevent conflicts of interest between itself, its funding providers and the interests of consumers.”¹³¹ The focus on these procedures indicates that the influence to be prevented under this rule is structural in nature and does not refer to a particular funding arrangement for a given case. Such procedures could, for example, seek to ensure that the qualified entity does not obtain funding exclusively from one funder or does not have personnel of funders from which the qualified entity derives funding in a controlling management position. In essence, what Art. 4(3)(e) Directive refers to are *governance rules and practices* for qualified entities, and not a different level of funder influence in any given case than Art. 10(2) Directive permits.

Article 4(3)(f) Directive provides that a qualified entity designated for cross-border actions

“makes publicly available in plain and intelligible language by any appropriate means, in particular on its website, information that demonstrates that the entity complies with the criteria listed in points [Art. 4(3)](a) to (e) and information about the sources of its

¹³¹ See also Recital 25 RAD.

*funding in general, its organi[z]ational, management and membership structure, its statutory purpose and its activities.*¹³²

e) *Options for Funders to Obtain their Return*

One aspect which is not explicitly addressed in the Directive, but which is of significant importance, is how a funder may eventually *obtain the return* on their investment.

The first option is that the funder receives a *part of the damages* award, with the funder's return being deducted from the amount the consumers will receive.¹³³ The legal basis for such a deduction could either be a contractual relationship which claimholders would enter into when they opt into a representative action.¹³⁴ In opt-out cases, such a *contractual* relationship would be difficult to arrange. An alternative solution would be the so-called *common fund doctrine* – ideally put into statutory form – according to which a deduction is justified as compensation for the contribution to establishing or increasing the common recovery fund for claimholders.¹³⁵ One obstacle to such a solution might be Art. 12(2) Directive, according to which consumers should not bear the costs of the proceedings.¹³⁶ However, in the European Commission's view, this provision does not apply to a success fee to be deducted from the sums awarded.¹³⁷ In addition, under Art. 20(3) Directive, consumers may be asked to pay a moderate entry fee or similar charge to participate, which could also take the form of a contribution to the success fee of the funder.¹³⁸

¹³² Emphasis added.

¹³³ European Commission, "Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities", Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 2.

¹³⁴ M. Legg, "Reconciling Litigation Funding and the Opt Out Group Definition in Federal Court of Australia Class Actions. The Need for a Legislative Common Fund Approach" (2011) in *Civil Justice Quarterly*, Vol. 30(1), pp. 52-73, at 59.

¹³⁵ M. Legg, "Reconciling Litigation Funding and the Opt Out Group Definition in Federal Court of Australia Class Actions. The Need for a Legislative Common Fund Approach" (2011) in *Civil Justice Quarterly*, Vol. 30(1), pp. 52-73; M. Piletta Massaro, "The New Directive on an EU-Wide Representative Action and Third-Party Litigation Funding: An Opportunity for European Consumers?" (2021) in *Revija Kopaoničke škole prirodnog prava*, Vol. 3(1), pp. 95-117, at 111-113.

¹³⁶ B. Gsell, "Europäische Verbandsklagen zum Schutz kollektiver Verbraucherinteressen – Königs- oder Holzweg?" (2021) in *Zeitschrift für Bank- und Kapitalmarktrecht BKR*, Vol. 21(9), pp. 521-529, at 527; see Recital 38 RAD.

¹³⁷ European Commission, "Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities", Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed December 15, 2021), at 4.

¹³⁸ But see B. Gsell, "The New European Directive on Representative Actions for the Protection of the Collective Interests of Consumers – A Huge, But Blurry Step Forward" (2021) in *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 58(5), pp. 1365-1400, at 1396-1398.

A second solution would be that the funder's success fee is part of an *adverse cost order* and, therefore, to be paid by the defendant.¹³⁹ Such a cost order against the defendant is for example possible under Dutch law.¹⁴⁰ However, the Directive restricts adverse cost orders to costs that were necessary.¹⁴¹ Therefore, the question will have to be answered whether and under what circumstances a funder's involvement in an action is necessary. This, in turn, may depend on alternatively available funding options. If such options are not available, there is indeed an argument to be made that the funder's fee was necessary and, therefore, should be part of recoverable costs. In addition, Art. 12(1) Directive grants Member States some leeway in designing their cost rules as it respects "conditions and exceptions provided for in national law applicable to court proceedings in general," so that such a solution might be compatible with the Directive.

Finally, a third solution would be that the funder's remuneration comes from the *funds which are not claimed* by consumers within the set time limit. Article 9(7) Directive provides that Member States should establish time limits for consumers to claim their benefit from redress measures and determine the destination of the funds which are not claimed within the time limit.¹⁴² This approach seems particularly realistic in opt-out regimes, where the unclaimed amounts tend to be higher than in opt-in regimes.¹⁴³

D. Conclusion

The Representative Actions Directive is a significant step in the EU's journey towards a more effective enforcement of consumer law in dispersed and mass harm situations. TPF has the potential to play a significant role in helping consumers to access justice by providing the

¹³⁹ European Commission, "Thematic debate on funding of actions and public assistance to qualified entities", Discussion Paper (2021) available at <https://prod5.assets-cdn.io/event/7409/assets/8362336747-054d358f5f.pdf> (accessed November 23, 2021), at 2; for a discussion of this approach under German law see A. Siebert-Reimer, *Der Anspruch auf Erstattung der Kosten der Prozessfinanzierung* (Duncker & Humblot: 2017).

¹⁴⁰ I.N. Tzankova and X.E. Kramer, "From Injunction and Settlement to Action: Collective Redress and Funding in the Netherlands" in A. Uzelac and S. Voet (eds.), *Class Actions in Europe. Holy Grail or Wrong Trail?* (Springer: 2021), pp. 97-130, at 117.

¹⁴¹ Recital 38 RAD.

¹⁴² See Recital 51 RAD.

¹⁴³ See for a practical example the arrangement of the consumer association Ius Omnibus: "The funder assumes all of Ius Omnibus's costs of the litigation and all its risks. It will only recoup its investment if the action is successful, if and to the extent the Court authorizes it, and if enough money remains in the global compensation fund, after distribution of compensations to consumers who request their share. Under these conditions, Ius Omnibus committed to returning to the funder the money it invested, plus a fair remuneration for the risk and time it was deprived of its capital, the proportionality of which will be assessed and controlled by the Court." available at <https://iusomnibus.eu/ius-omnibus-v-mastercard/> (accessed December 15, 2021).

liquidity and assuming the cost risk associated with representative actions. While the Directive allows TPF in principle, it prohibits certain problematic funding constellations and puts limits on the influence a funder may exert in a given case and, thereby, restricts some active forms of TPF. To what extent TPF will actually be available, and what role funders can play, depends to a large extent on the transposition legislation Member States will adopt. Therefore, the fights between business lobbyists and consumer organizations that have been fought over the last 20 years leading up to the Directive will likely be continued in the parliaments of the Member States. It will be interesting to see where we stand two years from now, after the Member States have implemented the Directive and the first cases have been filed, with or without the support of TPF.